

Analytical Method Development and Greenness Evaluation of a UV Spectrophotometric Technique for the Combined Estimation of Silodosin and Tadalafil

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ABSTRACT

Background: A green, UV spectrophotometric method was validated and developed for the simultaneous quantification of Silodosin and Tadalafil in a synthetic mixture. The method employs absorbance measurements at 269 nm for Silodosin and 284 nm for Tadalafil. **Methods:** Method validation was conducted following ICH Q2(R1) guidelines, evaluating parameters such as specificity, linearity, range, precision, accuracy, detection limit (DL), quantification limit (QL), and robustness. Linearity was established over the concentration ranges of 8–40 µg/mL for Silodosin and 5–25 µg/mL for Tadalafil. **Results:** The method exhibited excellent linearity ($R^2 > 0.999$), high precision (%RSD < 2%), and acceptable accuracy, with recovery values ranging from 98% to 102%. Robustness testing confirmed the method's reliability under small deliberate changes in analytical conditions. The developed method was successfully applied to the analysis of synthetic mixture. Environmental impact was assessed using GAPI, AGREE, AGREEprep, and the recently introduced BAGI tools, all indicating a favorable greenness profile. **Conclusion:** This UV spectrophotometric method was validated and is simple, sensitive, eco-friendly, and economical, making it suitable for the routine quality control of Silodosin and Tadalafil in pharmaceutical bulk formulations.

Keywords: Silodosin, Tadalafil, Simultaneous Estimation, UV Spectrophotometry, Method Validation, Green Analytical Chemistry

INTRODUCTION

Fig. 1. Structure of Silodosin

Silodosin, chemically designated as 1-(3-hydroxypropyl)-5-[2-[2-[2-(2,2,2-trifluoroethoxy)phenoxy]ethylamino]propyl]-2,3-dihydroindole-7-carboxamide, is an α_1 -adrenergic receptor blocker commonly prescribed to manage benign prostatic hyperplasia (BPH). It improves urinary symptoms such as weak stream, urgency, and frequent urination by relaxing smooth muscle in the prostate and bladder neck [2,3].

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Fig. 2. Structure of Tadalafil

Tadalafil, known chemically as 6-(1,3-benzodioxol-5-yl)-2-methyl-2,3,6,7,12,12a-hexahydro-pyrazino[1',2':1,6]pyrido[3,4-b]indole-1,4-dione, is a phosphodiesterase type 5 (PDE5) inhibitor. It works by increasing cyclic GMP levels, which leads to vasodilation and smooth muscle relaxation. Tadalafil is widely used for treating erectile dysfunction and BPH, either individually or in combination with other therapies [4,5].

In October 2023, the CDSCO approved a FDC of silodosin (8 mg) and tadalafil (5 mg) in hard gelatin capsules for the treatment of BPH with coexisting erectile dysfunction. This dual-acting therapy enhances both urinary function and erectile performance, providing a comprehensive treatment option.

While various analytical methods such as HPLC, HPTLC, and stability studies have been reported for the individual analysis of silodosin and tadalafil, there is a notable lack of UV spectrophotometric method was validated for their simultaneous estimation. This study aims to bridge that gap by developing and validating a UV-based method following the ICH Q2(R2) guidelines [1,6–23].

In recent years, the environmental sustainability of analytical methods has gained growing importance. Green chemistry metrics—including GAPI (Green Analytical Procedure Index), AGREE (Analytical GREEnness Metric), BAGI (Blue Applicability Grade Index)—help assess and improve the environmental friendliness of analytical methods. These tools evaluate parameters such as solvent use, energy efficiency, waste generation, and reagent

toxicity, making them essential for developing greener analytical practices [24].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Instruments and Reagents

Absorbance readings were recorded using a Shimadzu UV-1900 double-beam spectrophotometer with UV Probe 2.70 software and a 1 cm quartz cell across a wavelength range of 200–400 nm. A REPTech analytical balance (accuracy: 0.001 g) was used for weighing samples. FTIR analyses were performed using an Agilent Cary 630 FTIR spectrometer with MicroLab Expert software.

Silodosin and tadalafil API samples were generously supplied by Sun Pharmaceutical Industries Ltd. All reagents and solvents used were of analytical grade. Methanol (Rankem) was used as the solvent throughout the study.

2.2 Method Development

2.2.1 API Characterization

Melting points were determined using the capillary method with a Thiele's tube, using liquid paraffin for silodosin and silicone oil for tadalafil. FTIR spectra were collected using the KBr pellet method to confirm the presence of characteristic functional groups.

2.2.2 Solvent Selection

Solubility testing was performed in distilled water, methanol, DMSO, and DMF. Silodosin was highly soluble in methanol, and tadalafil was slightly soluble. Given methanol's solubility profile, economicalness, and compatibility, it was chosen for all subsequent procedures.

2.2.3 Wavelength Selection

UV spectra of standard solutions of silodosin (8 µg/mL) and tadalafil (5 µg/mL) were scanned from 200–400 nm. Overlay spectra revealed maximum absorbance at 269 nm for silodosin and 284 nm for tadalafil—wavelengths used for simultaneous quantification.

2.2.4 Standard Stock Preparation

Sildenafil and tadalafil were each weighed (50 mg), dissolved in methanol, and diluted to obtain 1000 µg/mL stock solutions. These were further diluted to prepare 100 µg/mL working solutions. Calibration standards were prepared in the ranges of 8–40 µg/mL for sildenafil and 5–25 µg/mL for tadalafil.

2.2.5 Sample Preparation

A synthetic mixture was prepared using excipients listed in patent WO 2014/209087 A1. A known amount of excipients (placebo), sildenafil (8 mg), and tadalafil (5 mg) were mixed, sonicated in methanol, filtered, and diluted to achieve concentrations of 8 µg/mL and 5 µg/mL, respectively.

2.2.6. Validation of the UV Spectrophotometric Method

The method was validated in accordance with ICH Q2(R2) (2023) guidelines.

1. Linearity:

Calibration curves were constructed at five concentration levels: 8–40 µg/mL for sildenafil and 5–25 µg/mL for tadalafil. Absorbance was plotted against concentration, and the regression equations and correlation coefficients (R^2) were calculated.

2. Precision:

- Repeatability: Six replicates of 24 µg/mL sildenafil and 15 µg/mL tadalafil were analyzed.
- Intra-day precision: Three concentrations (16, 24, and 32 µg/mL for sildenafil; 10, 15, and 20 µg/mL for tadalafil) were analyzed three times within the same day.
- Inter-day precision: The same concentrations were analyzed on three consecutive days. %RSD values were calculated for each.

3. Accuracy:

Recovery studies were performed using the standard addition method at 80%, 100%, and 120% levels. Known amounts of sildenafil (16 µg/mL) and tadalafil (10 µg/mL) were spiked into pre-analyzed samples.

Each level was analyzed in triplicate ($n = 3$), and the percent recovery was calculated.

4. Detection and Quantification Limits (DL and QL):

DL and QL were calculated from the standard deviation and slope of the calibration curve based on five replicates.

5. Robustness:

The robustness of the method was evaluated by making minor deliberate changes in wavelength (± 1 nm) and assessing the consistency of results.

6. Analysis of Synthetic Mixture:

Placebo mixture (based on patent WO 2014/209087 A1) and APIs (8 mg Sildenafil, 5 mg Tadalafil) were homogenized, dissolved in methanol, sonicated, filtered, and diluted to 8 µg/mL and 5 µg/mL, respectively.

3. GREENNESS ANALYSIS OF THE METHOD

Greenness evaluation of the method was conducted using four tools: GAPI, AGREE, BAGI, and AGREEprep. The GAPI pictogram was generated by assessing three key categories—sample preparation, solvent use, and instrumentation—represented on a color-coded pentagram where green, yellow, and red signify increasing levels of environmental impact, respectively. The AGREE pictogram was obtained by inputting data corresponding to the 12 principles of Green Analytical Chemistry (GAC), yielding a score between 0 and 1 for each principle. The BAGI tool was employed to assess the applicability of the analytical method based on ten criteria from White Analytical Chemistry (WAC), producing both a pictogram and an overall score that reflect the method's practicality and suitability. For AGREEprep, a greenness evaluation of the sample preparation procedure was performed using input data aligned with the ten principles of Green Sample Preparation (GSP), resulting in a circular pictogram with a central score, where 0 indicates higher environmental impact and 1 denotes an environmentally friendly approach.[25-30]

RESULTS

In this method, absorbance was measured at the two wavelengths corresponding to the λ_{max} of both Silodosin and Tadalafil. The simultaneous equation method was selected because, when a sample contains two absorbing drugs—each of which absorbs at the

maxi of the other—both drugs can be determined using this technique. The λ_{max} values of the two components should be sufficiently distinct, and the components should not chemically interact.

Fig. 3. Linearity spectra of Silodosin (8-40 $\mu\text{g/mL}$)

Fig. 4. Linearity of Tadalafil (5-25 $\mu\text{g/mL}$)

Fig. 5 Overlain spectra of Tadalafil (5 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) with Silodosin (8-40 $\mu\text{g/mL}$)

Fig. 6 Overlain spectra of Silodosin (8 µg/mL) with Tadalafil (5-25 µg/mL)

Fig. 7. Overlain spectra of Silodosin (8 ppm) and Tadalafil (5 ppm)

Linearity: Linearity was taken in range of 8-40 ppm for SLD and 5-25 ppm for TDF. The R^2 was found to be nearer to 0.9999. the data are mentioned in table.1

Table. 1. Optical characteristics for SLD and TDF:

PARAMETERS	SLD		TDF	
	269 nm	284 nm	269 nm	284 nm
Detection wavelength	269 nm	284 nm	269 nm	284 nm
Beers law limit	8-40 ppm		5-25 ppm	
Regression equation	$y = 0.0187x + 0.0141$	$y = 0.0065x + 0.0078$	$y = 0.0274x + 0.0119$	$y = 0.0202x + 0.0799$
Correlation coefficient	0.9937	0.9973	0.9996	0.9961

Precision: The repeatability, intraday, interday precision were performed for both drugs at mentioned concentrations for SLD and TDF, respectively at both

the wavelengths. The % RSD was less than 2.0. the data are presented in table. 2

Table 2. Precision data for SLD and TDF:

Repeatability			
DRUGS	CONC. ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	%RSD	
		269 nm	284 nm
SLD	24	1.0014	1.7987
TDF	15	0.7867	0.9044
Intraday Precision			
SLD	16	1.4526	1.9215
	24	0.4435	0.9352
	32	0.6877	1.7419
TDF	10	1.6371	0.5166
	15	0.8709	1.3481
	20	0.9794	0.6596
Interday Precision			
SLD	16	1.8955	1.9394
	24	0.9136	1.2719
	32	0.7463	1.8856
TDF	10	1.8437	1.0297
	15	1.1405	0.9449
	20	0.9889	0.9429

Accuracy: The accuracy was performed were for SLD 16 ppm conc. was taken and for TDF 10 ppm conc. The datas are mentioned in table. 3. The accuracy data shows that % Recovery was found between 98-102 %.

Table 3. Accuracy data for SLD and TDF:

Drug	Level (%)	Total amount of solution ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	% Recovery	
			269 nm	284 nm
SLD	0	16	98.95	99.18
	80	28.8	99.31	98.93
	100	32	99.86	99.61
	120	35.2	99.34	99.74
TDF	0	10	100.76	100.23
	80	18	101.19	101.23
	100	20	100.75	100.52
	120	22	100.05	100.61

Assay:

Table 4. Assay for SLD and TDF:

Actual concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)		Amount obtained mean \pm S.D (n=3)	% Purity of SLD \pm S.D (n=3)	% Purity of TDF \pm S.D (n=3)
SLD	8	7.9904 \pm 0.0252	99.88 \pm 0.7451	99.63 \pm 0.5246
TDF	5	4.9815 \pm 0.0458		

Detection Limit (DL) and Quantitation Limit (QL):

The DL and QL were found to be 0.63 µg/mL and 1.91 µg/mL for Silodosin and 0.19 µg/mL and 0.58 µg/mL for Tadalafil at 269 nm. At 284 nm, the DL and QL were 0.97 µg/mL and 2.93 µg/mL for Silodosin and 0.69 µg/mL and 2.09 µg/mL for Tadalafil.

Robustness:

Robustness was evaluated at 269 nm and 284 nm for Silodosin (8 ppm) and Tadalafil (5 ppm), respectively. Using wavelength as the parameter, and analyzing three replicates, the %RSD was found to be less than 2.0%.

GREENNESS ASSESSMENT:

The greenness assessment of the developed method was carried out using four different tools, as shown in Table 5.

The GAPI tool indicated seven green fields (principles 1, 3, 8, 9, 10, 11, and 12), six yellow fields (principles 2, 4, 5, 13, 14, and 15), and one red field (principle 7), classifying the method as moderately green.

The AGREE tool evaluation showed three dark green segments (principles 3, 4, and 6), four green (principles 1, 5, 8, and 12), four light green (principles 2, 7, 11), one yellow (principle 10), and one orange (principle 9), resulting in a total AGREE score of 0.74, suggesting the method is green.

According to the BAGI tool, criteria 1, 5, 7, 8, and 10 strongly aligned with the White Analytical Chemistry (WAC) principles, with a total BAGI score of 82.5.

The AGREEprep tool analysis revealed three dark green segments (principles 1, 8, and 10), four light green (principles 4, 5, 6, and 9), two yellow (principles 3 and 7), and one orange (principle 2), with a total AGREEprep score of 0.70, confirming that the sample preparation process was environmentally friendly.

Table 5. Results of greenness assessment of the proposed method was performed using four different tools

Name of tool	Score	Pictogram
AGREE	0.74	
AGREEprep	0.70	

BAGI	82.5	
GAPI	-	

Table. 6. Summary for Simultaneous Equation Method for SLD and TDF:

PARAMETERS	SILODOSIN		TADALAFIL	
	8-40 µg/mL		5-25 µg/mL	
Linearity (n=5)	269 nm	284 nm	269 nm	284 nm
Correlation coefficient (R ²) (n=5)	0.9937	0.9937	0.9996	0.9961
Repeatability (% RSD) (n=6)	1.00	1.79	0.79	0.90
Intraday precision (% RSD) (n=3)	0.44-1.45	0.93-1.92	0.87-1.63	0.52-1.34
Interday precision (% RSD) (n=3)	0.75-1.89	1.27-1.94	0.99-1.84	0.94-1.03
% Recovery (n=3)	98.95-99.86	98.93-99.74	100.05-101.19	100.23-101.23
DL (µg/mL) (n=5)	0.6289	0.9672	0.1908	0.6905
QL (µg/mL) (n=5)	1.9058	2.9310	0.5783	2.0925
Assay % (n=3)	99.88		99.63	

DISCUSSION

The UV spectrophotometric method developed in this study marks a significant advancement in pharmaceutical analysis, especially for combination therapies targeting benign prostatic hyperplasia and erectile dysfunction. It enables simultaneous quantification of Silodosin and Tadalafil in fixed-dose combinations (FDCs), addressing a gap in current

literature where most methods target either drug individually. This dual-drug estimation is validated and well-suited for routine quality control applications.

Key advantages of the method include its simplicity, quick execution, and affordability, making it highly practical for use in manufacturing and regulatory settings. By consolidating the analysis of two drugs

into one procedure, the method enhances efficiency, reduces solvent and reagent usage, and supports sustainable laboratory practices.

To evaluate the method's environmental friendliness, greenness assessment tools such as GAPI, AGREE, AGREEprep, and BAGI were applied. GAPI indicated low solvent use, minimal sample volume, and straightforward sample preparation. AGREE and AGREEprep scores affirmed the method's eco-friendly profile, highlighting the use of water or safer solvents, the absence of derivatization, and low energy needs. BAGI offered a comprehensive green performance overview, underscoring safety and waste minimization. However, the method's validation was limited to a single formulation under controlled conditions. Broader validation across various formulations, excipients, and production batches is necessary to confirm its robustness. Future studies may also explore its application to other multi-component formulations and its potential for real-time monitoring. In conclusion, this is the first validated UV spectrophotometric method for concurrent estimation of Silodosin and Tadalafil in combined dosage forms. It offers analytical reliability, environmental sustainability, and cost-effectiveness, supporting its use in routine quality control and advancing green pharmaceutical analysis.

CONCLUSION

A robust and validated UV spectrophotometric method was developed for the simultaneous determination of Silodosin and Tadalafil in synthetic mixtures. The method showed satisfactory linearity, precision, accuracy, and robustness per ICH guidelines. Its practicality and reliability support its use in early-stage formulation and routine quality testing. Greenness evaluations via GAPI, AGREE, BAGI, and AGREEprep confirmed its minimal environmental impact, reinforcing its role in sustainable pharmaceutical practices. Further validation on commercial formulations and under varied conditions is recommended.

This study contributes to the limited literature on the simultaneous analysis of these two APIs and offers a cost-effective solution for early formulation studies. Future research should focus on applying this method to marketed dosage forms and further evaluating its

performance under various formulation and environmental conditions. Furthermore, environmental impact was assessed using GAPI, AGREE, BAGI, and AGREEprep tools, with favorable outcomes indicating low ecological burden and minimal waste generation.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS:

SLD: Silodosin, TDF: Tadalafil, UV: Ultra-violet, SD: Standard Deviation, ED: Erectile dysfunction, BPH: Benign Prostatic Hyperplasia, RSD: Relative Standard Deviation, STD: Standard, CDSCO: Central Drug Standard Control Organization, FDC: fixed-dose combination, ICH: International Conference on Harmonization, μm : Micrometer, $\mu\text{g/mL}$: microgram/millilitre; Avg: Average IUPAC: International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry, mg: Milligram, API: Active Pharmaceutical Ingredients, v/v Volume by volume, w/v Weight by volume, wt. Weight, R^2 : Co-relation coefficient, ppm Parts per million, ANOVA: Analysis of Variance, DL: Detection limit, QL: Quantitation Limit, AGREE: Analytical GREENness, GAPI: Green Analytical Procedure Index, BAGI: Blue Applicability Grade Index.

DECLARATIONS

Ethics approval and consent to participate

Not applicable. This study did not involve human participants or animal subjects.

Consent for publication

Not applicable.

Availability of data and material

All data generated or analyzed during this study are included in this published article. Additional details can be provided by the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

Funding:

This research did not receive any specific grant from funding agencies in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

Authors' contributions

Yukti Rana, Prachi Patel, Umang Rachhadiya: Conceptualization, Method development, Experimental analysis, Drafting of the manuscript

Yukti Rana, Prachi Patel, Umang Rachhadiya, Yash Sheth, Mahammadjed Badem, MuhammadOvais Patel: Method validation, Data analysis, Review and editing

Dr. Drashti Mandale, Dr. Nidhi Chauhan: Supervision, Final approval of the manuscript

All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

Studies involving plants

Not applicable. This study did not involve the use of plants.

Acknowledgement

The authors would like to extend heartfelt thanks to the Department of Pharmacy, Laxminarayandev College of Pharmacy for providing the laboratory facilities and academic support required to complete this research. We are deeply grateful to our research guide, Dr. Drashti Mandale, for their expert supervision, constructive feedback, and continuous encouragement throughout the project.

We also appreciate the support of our colleagues and lab technicians, whose assistance was invaluable during the experimental and analytical phases of the study.

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HOW TO CITE: Rana Yukti*, Patel Prachi, Rachhadiya Umang, Sheth Yash, Badem Mahammadjed, Patel MuhammadOvais Drashti Mandale, Nidhi Chauhan, Analytical Method Development and Greenness Evaluation of a UV Spectrophotometric Technique for the Combined Estimation of Silodosin and Tadalafil, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 2026, 2 (1), 1105-1116.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18365548>

